

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**INCIDENCE OF CUTANEOUS LEISHMANIASIS IN AL-AHSA,
SAUDI ARABIA FROM 2011 TO 2013**Yosuf Yaqub Alarfaj¹, Nouh Ibrahim Alghanim^{1*}, Ridha Hussain Alkhalifah¹,
Meshel Salah Balghonaim¹, Mohamed Bahgat Ali¹¹College of Medicine, King Faisal University, Al-Ahsa, Saudi Arabia**Abstract**

Background: Different studies showed a fluctuating incidence of Cutaneous Leishmaniasis (CL) cases in correlation to age, gender, ethnicity, area, and season in Al-Ahsa, Saudi Arabia.

Aim of the study: We aimed to study the epidemiological trends of Cutaneous Leishmaniasis in Al-Ahsa, Saudi Arabia.

Materials & Methods: In this retrospective study, data gathered from the Vector Control Unit was analyzed. All the reported cases starting from 2011 to 2013 were included in the study. The total number of cases were 761.

Results: The findings clearly showed an increase in the incidence of CL in the study years from 2011 to 2013. The number of cases started to increase in December and reached its peak in January. We found exceptionally high incidence in some districts e.g. Al-Jarn (471/100,000). The incidence was significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher in non-Saudis (73.4/100000) than in Saudis (10.3/100000), and in males than in females. The ratio of the non-Saudis to Saudis was 7:1. The general ratio between males and females was (7.2:1). The male to female ratio was (2.8:1) in Saudis, and (27.03:1) in non-Saudis. The mean age was (29.68±13.6). The distribution of CL showed variation among non-Saudi nationalities with Indians, Egyptians, Bangladeshis and Nepalese more affected.

Conclusions: There was an absolute increase in the cases of CL in Al-Ahsa from 2011 to 2013. Since non-Saudis are more susceptible to the disease, there is a need to increase awareness among non-Saudis. In addition, control measures should be concentrated towards the areas with exceptionally high incidence.

Keywords: Leishmaniasis, Cutaneous, Al-Ahsa, Incidence, Saudi Arabia.

Corresponding author:**Nouh Ibrahim Alghanim,**

College of Medicine, King Faisal University, Al-Ahsa, Saudi Arabia,

E-mail: nowah2008@gmail.com,

Telephone number: +966594449313.

QR code

Please cite this article in press Nouh Ibrahim Alghanim et al., **Incidence of Cutaneous Leishmaniasis In Al-Ahsa, Saudi Arabia From 2011 To 2013.**, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2019; 06(01).

INTRODUCTION:

Cutaneous leishmaniasis is a parasitic disease caused by leishmania parasites and transmitted by sandflies. It produces skin ulcerations with raised borders which may last months to years and typically result in severe scarring [1]. In 2010, the WHO has estimated that 1.5 million new CL cases occur yearly and that 12 million people are infected globally [2]. Although CL (globally widely distributed) affects 88 countries, 90% of CL cases occur in only seven countries including Saudi Arabia [3]. Cutaneous leishmaniasis (CL) is endemic in different districts in Saudi Arabia including Alhasa, Qaseem, Aseer, Hail, Madina, etc [4-7]. The (CL) is caused by both *L. major* and *L. tropica* but *L. major* appears to be widely distributed in the Kingdom [7-8]. Al-Ahsa showed the highest incidence of CL (41.2 %) all over the kingdom in year 2001. In year 2004, the incidence in Al-Ahsa declined to 20.9% but still it was the second highest incidence in the kingdom after Qaseem (26.6%) [4].

Different studies showed variation in incidence of CL correlated to age, gender, ethnicity, affected anatomical sites, area (rural, urban) and seasons [5,6,8-14]. Different studies in Al-Ahsa, showed that the incidence is variable (increase, decrease or fluctuating) in different years of different studies [5,6]. Amin *et al.* (2013), studied the epidemiological trends of (CL) in Al-Ahsa from 2000 – 2010 and reported decrease of the incidence of (CL) in years 2008 – 2010. The incidence was lowest in year 2008 but showed slight increase in years 2009 and 2010 in both Saudi and expatriates' patients [6]. Although variability in CL incidence among Saudi and non-Saudi was confirmed by the previous studies, no study assessed the incidence of CL in different nationality of expatriates. Seasonal variability of CL incidence also proved effect of weather changes.

The current study was conducted to answer the following questions: (1) What is the incidence of CL in Al-Ahsa according to gender, age, ethnicity (nationality), area (rural, urban) and seasons in recent years; 2011 - 2013? And its relation to previous period, (2) How CL incidence is influenced by residence and season? (3) What is the incidence of CL in different nationalities of expatriates (Egyptian, Indian, Pakistani, etc)? We have tried to correlate our data as a follow up to the most recent study in Al-

Ahsa by Amin *et al.* (2013), which covered the epidemiology of CL in the same region over 11 years (from 2000 to 2010) [6].

MATERIAL AND METHODS:**Study area**

Al-Ahsa is governorate located in Eastern Province, Saudi Arabia. Al-Ahsa has a population of 1,165,422 in 2013. The urban areas include Al-Hufuf, Al-Mubarraz and Al-Oyun, with a population of 583,925. The rural areas include eastern villages, northern villages and migrations e.g. Al-Ghoibah with a population of 581,497. Northern Villages consist of Al-Jarn, Al-Marah, Al-Shigaig, Al-Julaijlah and other small villages. Eastern villages has more districts than the northern villages, which include Al-Omran, Al-Holailah, Al-Garah, Al-Towaitair and others [15].

Data collection and analysis

This research is a retrospective study based on Vector Control Unit database of reported CL cases in Al-Ahsa from 2011-2013. The database was reached after agreement between King Faisal University and Vector Control Unit. Vector Control Unit collected the reported cases from three specialized clinics of leishmaniasis that cover 58 primary health centers, 30 centers in urban areas and 28 in rural and Bedouin areas. The cases were gathered by VCU on a weekly basis from the three specialized clinics after diagnosis. This study included all the notified cases from 2011 to 2013, which were 761 cases. The study will investigate through biographical and clinical data, including age, sex, nationality, area. Data were entered and analyzed by using SPSS version 17 (SPSS inc., Chicago. IL, USA).

RESULTS:**Incidence of CL:**

During the period of 2011-2013, a total number of 761 cases (219, 246, 296 in the study years respectively) were reported in Al-Ahsa by Vector Control Unit. There was significant increase in the number of cases starting from 2011 to 2013. The number of cases increased by 12.3% in 2012. Then, it continued to increase by 20.3% in 2013. The total increase from 2011 to 2013 was 35.2%. The incidence per 100,000 was 19.7, 21.6 and 25.3 in years 2011, 2012 and 2013 respectively. (Table 1)

Table (1): The incidence of cutaneous leishmaniasis per 100,000 among Saudis and non-Saudis in Al-Ahsa, Saudi Arabia from 2011 to 2013.

Years	Total (Per 100,000)	Saudi (Per 100,000)	Non-Saudi (Per 100,000)
2011	219 (19.7)	87 (9.6)	132 (64.4)
2012	246 (21.6)	103(11.1)	143 (66.9)
2013	296 (25.3)	98 (10.3)	198 (89.1)
Total	761 (22.2)	288 (10.3)	473 (73.4)

Gender Distribution:

The reported cases of CL included 668 males and 93 females. The distribution of cases was significantly higher in males than females ($P<0.05$). As Figure 1

shows, the percentage of cases tends to increase among males and decrease among females. In 2013, 89.53% of the cases was males and 10.47% was females. The male to female ratio was 7.2:1.0.

Figure 1: Distribution of CL cases according to gender in Al-Ahsa Saudi Arabia from 2011 – 2013.

Age Distribution:

The age of the cases ranged from 6 months to 80 years. As Figure 2 shows, most of the reported cases

were in the age group 21-40 (58.5%). There were only a few cases of patients older than 60 years (11 cases,1.4%). The mean age was 29.68 SD \pm 13.6.

Figure 2: Distribution of CL cases according to age groups in Al-Ahsa Saudi Arabia from 2011 – 2013.

Distribution by nationalities (Saudi – Non Saudi):

The distribution of cases among non-Saudis was significantly higher than in Saudis ($P < 0.05$). The reported cases were 288 (37.8%) Saudis, mean age 22.76 SD \pm 16.48, and 473 (62.2%) non-Saudis, mean age 33.89 SD \pm 9.25. Table 1 shows the calculated incidence per 100,000 among Saudis and non-Saudis. Affected Saudis tend to be younger than affected non-Saudis.

Distribution among Non Saudi nationalities:

There was variation in the distribution of CL among different non-Saudi nationalities. From 473 cases reported in non-Saudis, 157 (33.2%) Indians, 93 (19.7%) Egyptians, 62 (13.1%) Bangladeshis, 49 (10.4%) Nepalese, 39 (8.2%) Pakistanis and 18 (3.8%) Filipino. The remaining 55 cases (11.6%) were reported in other 7 nationalities (Table 2).

Table (2): Distribution of cutaneous leishmaniasis among different foreign nationalities in Al-Ahsa, Saudi Arabia from 2011 to 2013.

Year	Nationality							Total (100%)
	Indian	Egyptian	Bangladeshi	Nepali	Pakistani	Filipino	Others	
2011	42 (31.8%)	24 (18.2%)	21(15.9%)	19(14.4%)	5 (3.8%)	5 (3.8%)	16 (12.1%)	132
2012	50 (35.0%)	29 (20.3%)	11 (7.7%)	16 (11.2%)	11 (7.7%)	7 (4.9%)	19 (13.3%)	143
2013	65 (32.8%)	40 (20.2%)	30 (15.2%)	14 (7.1%)	23 (11.6%)	6(3.0%)	20(10.1%)	198
Total	157 (33.2%)	93(19.7%)	62(13.1%)	49(10.4%)	39 (8.2%)	18 (3.8%)	55 (11.6%)	473

Distribution by Locality:

The majority of the reported cases were in rural areas. The incidence rate showed an increase in the rural areas from 2011 to 2013 (76.48%). The incidence rate was higher (33.3/100,000) in rural areas than in urban areas (10.2/100,000). Among the urban areas Al-Oyun had the highest incidence rate (57/100,000) while Al-Hufuf and Al-Mubarraz together accounted for lower incidence rate (7/100 000). There were 87

cases in Al-Hufuf (35% in King Fahad District only). The incidence rate in King Fahad District was 53.9 per 100,000. Regarding rural areas, there were 252 cases in Eastern Villages (39% in Al-Omran Village) and 183 cases in the north villages (47% in Al-Jarn Village.) The incidence rate was 471/100,000 in Al-Jarn Village, 348.4/100,000 in Al-Ghoibah and 125.3/100,000 in Al-Omran Village. (Table 3)

Table (3): The incidence of cutaneous leishmaniasis cases per 100,000 distributed by locality in Al-Ahsa, Saudi Arabia from 2011 to 2013.

Year	Urban				Rural		
	Al-Oyun	King Fahd District	Al-Hufuf	Al-Mubarraz	Al-Jarn	Al-Ghoibah	Al-Omran
2011	34.8	103	11	5.1	347.3	261.5	70.4
2012	68.1	44.5	10	5.1	559.4	173.2	177.6
2013	73.3	26.1	13.1	6.6	406	634.1	144.3
Average	57	53	11.2	5.5	471	348.4	125.3

Seasonal Distribution:

The number of cases started to increase in December and reached its peak in January. Then, it declined and

fluctuated. April had the fewest number of cases. (Figure 3)

Figure 3: Monthly distribution of CL cases in Al-Ahsa Saudi Arabia from 2011 – 2013.

DISCUSSION:

Different studies have been performed to assess the epidemiology of CL in Al-Ahsa. The first study was a large retrospective study conducted by Al-Tawfiq and Abu Khamsin which covered the epidemiology in the eastern province including Al-Ahsa for 46 years (1956-2002). The incidence reached an epidemic proportion in 1973 and thereafter declined to stable rate since 1987 [5]. The next study conducted by Amin et al in Al-Ahsa (2000-2010) [6] confirmed the declining trend in the rate of CL incidence reported by Al-Tawfiq and Abu Khamsin study. However, our study which covered 761 cases showed an interesting finding that the rate of incidence for CL was increasing gradually during the study period (2011-2013). The overall incidence per 100,000 population was 19.7, 21.6 and 25.3 in the studied years 2011, 2012 and 2013 respectively.

Our study confirmed the higher incidence of CL among non-Saudi as compared to Saudi population reported by Amin et al. which started at 2003 and continued in the remaining period of their study till 2010 [6]. Our results revealed that the incidence among Saudi was fluctuating in small range and averaged 10.3 per 100,000 population. The incidence increased (11.1/100,000) in 2012 then declined to (10.3/100000) in 2013. On the other hand, Non-Saudi incidence was higher and annually increasing to about seven times that of Saudi. It averaged 73.4 per 100,000 population. This could be attributed to the fact that better awareness and development of resistance to the parasite lower the incidence of Saudi cases while the lack of awareness among Non-Saudi increased their incidence rate. In addition, Non-Saudis often live in the rural areas which showed a higher incidence of CL than recorded in urban areas.

The current study revealed variations in regional distribution of CL in Al-Ahsa governorate. The majority of cases were in the rural areas (76.48%) with overall incidence of 33.3 per 100,000 population compared to 10.3/100,000 in urban areas. In rural area, some districts showed very high incidence. The highest overall incidences were recorded in Al-Jarn (471/100000), Al-Goibah (348.4/100000) and Al-Omran (125.3/100000). Moreover, the highest incidence in different study years was recorded in Al-Ghoibah in 2013 (634.1/100,000) after it has been declined from (261.5/100,000) in 2011 to (173.2 /100,000) in 2012. Al-Omran and Al-Jarn showed a higher incidence in 2012 as compared to other years (Al-Omran 70.4, 177.6, 144.3 respectively) and (Al-Jarn 347.3, 599.4, 406 respectively).

The average incidence in the two main cities (Al-Hufuf and Al-Mubarratz) was 7/100,000. Among the urban areas, Al-Oyun showed the highest incidence averaged 57/100,000 followed by King Fahd district (a district in Al-Hufuf city) with average incidence 53/100,000. This can be explained by the nature of these areas in which many farms are located and considered as good places where the vector lives. Although King Fahd district had a high incidence among urban areas, it declined from 2011 to 2013 (103, 44.5, 26.1 respectively). In the other hand, the incidence in Al-Oyun was increasing constantly during the study period (34.8, 68.1, 73.3, respectively).

Our results revealed seasonal distribution of CL similar to that reported by previous studies in Al-Ahsa. The incidence in our and other studies started to increase in September and reached its peak in January. This increase in the incidence is seen only in winter period, which means that the infection is more prevalent in the winter season. This can be explained by increase in the activity of the sandflies in winter period [13].

Our results showed that about 60% of cases appeared in the 21-40 years age group. Some previous studies reported that majority of the cases occurred in middle aged people [13,16,17]. However, other studies have recorded that the disease was most prevalent in >15 years age group [5,6]. On the other hand, in the previous studies, the prevalence was in ≤ 15 age group in which most cases were for indigenous people. This can be explained by the fact that Saudis have developed resistance to CL due to their previous exposure to the parasite, and increased awareness [13].

Our results regarding the gender distribution

confirmed the finding of higher incidence in males than in females reported by Amin *et al.* [6] but the ratio in our study (7.2:1) was higher than the ratio in their study (3.6:1). This is contradictory to the study of Al-Tawfiq and Abu Khamsin where their study showed that CL affects both sexes equally. Our finding might be explained by the fact that males are more exposed to the vector than the females because the nature of their work field. In addition, it can be explained by the cultural costume of female, where they cover most of their body, so the vector cannot reach to their skin [18]. While our study shows a definite male preponderance, other studies have actually shown higher incidence in female [18,19].

CONCLUSION:

Our study has shown an increase in the incidence of CL from year 2011 to year 2013. Incidence of CL was seven times greater in non-Saudis than in Saudis and in males than in females. Incidence of CL was three times greater in rural as compared with urban areas. Moreover, some districts recorded very high incidence reached up to 634.1/100,000.

A new finding of our study revealed variability in the incidence of CL in different non-Saudi nationalities with highest number in Indians.

RECOMMENDATIONS:

1. It is important to increase the awareness of non-Saudis with brochures using different language with more concentration on Indian, Egyptian, Bangladeshis, Nepalese and Pakistanis.
2. Special attention should be paid for vector control unit and increasing awareness in districts with the highest incidence reported in our study (Al-Jarn, Al-Ghoibah, Al-Omran and Al-Oyun). These recommendations, if strictly followed, may lead to significant control of the disease in Al-Ahsa. From our experience, we found that such epidemiological study is very valuable for the community and so, we recommend repetition of similar studies in coming years.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT:

The authors thank Dr. Salah Mohammed Balghonaim, the director of vector control unit in Al-Ahsa, for his great help and for providing research data. Also, we thank Dr. Sayed Ibrahim for his guidance in preparation of the research statistics.

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